

PEER PRESSURE AND PERSONALITY TRAITS AS DETERMINANTS OF YOUTH RESTIVENESS IN KADUNA STATE UNIVERSITY, KADUNA

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Abstract

Youth restiveness within tertiary institutions poses serious challenges to academic activities, campus security, and social stability. This study investigated peer pressure and personality traits as determinants of youth restiveness among students of Kaduna State University. A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted. Data were collected using standardized questionnaires on peer pressure, personality traits, and restiveness. Data collected were analyzed using standard linear regression and multiple regression analysis. The study employed multistage sampling to select 370 participants aged 16 to 35 years. Three scales, namely the Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS), Ten Item Personality Inventory (TIPI), and Restiveness Factor Description, were used. The findings revealed that peer pressure significantly predicted restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University ($R = .179$, $R^2 = .032$, $F = 12.11$, $p < .05$), indicating that peer pressure accounted for 3.2% of the variance in restiveness. Hypothesis two also found that personality traits significantly predicted restiveness ($R = .226$, $R^2 = .051$, $F = 19.88$, $p < .05$), accounting for 5.1% of the variance in restiveness. Hypothesis three indicated that peer pressure and personality traits jointly and significantly predicted restiveness among youths ($R = .251$, $R^2 = .063$, $F = 12.32$, $p < .05$), jointly accounting for 6.3% of the variance in restiveness. Personality traits emerged as a relatively stronger predictor of restiveness than peer pressure. The study concluded that peer pressure and personality traits are significant determinants of restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. The study recommended that universities should strengthen counseling and psychological support services, implement peer mentoring programs, and develop intervention strategies aimed at improving emotional regulation, self-control, and positive peer interactions among students.

Keywords: Peer pressure, personality traits, youth restiveness, students

Introduction

Youth restiveness is a developmental milestone that describes the discontent and agitation young people experience, which frequently manifests as disruptive and occasionally violent behaviors. It includes a range of agitation, discontent, and deviant

conduct among young individuals, which has become a subject of growing concern in modern society. This phenomenon entails various actions and behaviors, spanning peaceful demonstrations and advocacy to instances of vandalism, substance misuse, and engagement in criminal acts (Uriah et al., 2014). Various parts of the world have experienced incidents of youth unrest, spanning peaceful protests to instances of vandalism and aggression. These displays of dissatisfaction and disillusionment among young individuals are indicative of deeper-rooted issues such as socioeconomic inequalities, political marginalization, cultural divides, and psychological pressures that influence their everyday realities (Omoike & Oviawe, 2018).

In Nigeria, youth restiveness has gained widespread attention, especially in recent times (Ojobah et al., 2020). Since the advent of the current democratic era, the nation has experienced numerous instances of violence and human rights violations perpetrated by restive youths across various regions. In some instances, these actions have resulted in significant loss of lives and property. According to Raymond and Austine (2020), the causes of youth restiveness are connected to unemployment, lack of basic and adequate infrastructural facilities, and inadequate social amenities, among others. The spiraling effect of youth restiveness is evident in Nigeria through ethnic militias, kidnapping, cultism, armed robbery, agitations, and involvement in social insecurity.

Akaenye and Esioboma (2025) identified peer pressure as one major determinant of youth restiveness. This influence is especially strong during adolescence and young adulthood, periods when individuals are particularly sensitive to social acceptance and the need to belong. It describes the power that peers have to compel an individual to adopt the norms, beliefs, and actions of the group. Peer pressure can take many different forms, ranging from tactful persuasion to direct intimidation (Laursen & Veenstra, 2021). To begin with, adolescence is a crucial developmental stage characterized by heightened sensitivity to social cues (Adimora et al., 2018). During this phase, people are more likely to prioritize social benefits over parental supervision or personal values in an effort to gain approval from their peers. For this reason, understanding peer pressure is essential for creating successful interventions that might lessen its sometimes harmful effects (Knoll et al., 2015). Secondly, peer pressure impacts cultural norms and larger social dynamics in addition to specific behavioral consequences. Peer pressure, for example, may propagate harmful habits, including substance misuse and delinquency, as well as beneficial behaviors such as academic excellence and healthy lifestyle choices. Although peer pressure can result in both positive and negative behaviors, it is frequently linked to the promotion of risky and antisocial conduct, such as the use of psychoactive substances, which is why it has a significant effect on young people (Egwuatu & Yahaya, 2023).

Personality traits are another major determinant of youth restiveness and are described as enduring characteristics that significantly affect how individuals think, feel, and act in different contexts. People with different personality traits may experience and react differently to the same situations and challenges, as personality shapes how people consistently perceive and handle their surroundings (Opoku et al., 2023). Personality encompasses the combination of characteristics and qualities that define an individual's unique character. It includes a variety of mental and emotional attributes that contribute to consistent patterns in how a person feels, thinks, and behaves. Exploring personality

involves examining the traits and processes that differentiate individuals, influencing their interactions with the environment and responses to various situations (Hampson, 2012). The Big Five personality traits include extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience. These traits are essential for understanding differences in behavior and responses to environmental stimuli among individuals.

In the context of youth restiveness, personality traits are crucial in determining how young people respond to social, economic, and political pressures (Egan, 2008). Understanding personality traits means recognizing that everyone has certain characteristic ways of behaving. People may be sociable or shy, passive or aggressive, optimistic or pessimistic. Thus, behavior, characteristics, thoughts, and feelings as habitual aspects of daily life can be considered personality traits. In the context of social life, personality traits are strongly influenced by the environment in which a person lives and associates with others, such as in friendship, education, family, and community settings. For instance, parents play an important role in shaping personality traits, and this role is also supported by the environment. They are a core point in the formation of behavior, thought, and self-control (Hampson, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

Youth restiveness in Nigeria is a major problem characterized by increased violence, substance abuse, delinquency, and other antisocial behaviors (Adegoke et al., 2023). Despite numerous government interventions, these efforts have yielded limited success, indicating a deeper underlying issue that remains inadequately addressed. One of the major influences on youth restive behavior is peer pressure, which shapes attitudes, behaviors, and decision-making processes, particularly among adolescents and young adults. The strong need for social acceptance often compels young individuals to conform to the expectations of their peer groups, even when those expectations involve engaging in delinquent activities (Albert et al., 2013). While peer influence can sometimes be positive, leading to academic motivation and community engagement, the prevalence of negative peer pressure, which encourages violence, drug use, and other deviant behaviors, remains a critical factor in youth restive behavior.

Nevertheless, limited empirical research exploring the specific ways in which peer dynamics contribute to this problem of youth restiveness within the region is available. Aina's (2025) investigation into the perceived causes of youth restiveness among undergraduates provides crucial context. The study links youth restiveness to factors such as governance failures and socioeconomic pressures, including unresponsive government, corruption, and unemployment. While Aina (2025) also identifies peer pressure as a major cause, the study does not delve into how peer dynamics operate or interact with individual personality traits. Therefore, this established understanding creates a platform for a more nuanced investigation. Consequently, this research seeks to build upon this foundation by moving beyond the identification of causes to examine the

interplay between peer pressure and personality traits in precipitating youth restiveness. The aim is to provide a psychologically informed analysis that can lead to more targeted and effective intervention strategies.

Furthermore, studies on youth restiveness in Nigeria focus on economic deprivation, political instability, and educational challenges, often neglecting the intricate psychological and social dimensions. Oke et al. (2024) framed youth restiveness as a critical national threat to Nigeria's peace, security, and development. They identify a broad range of causal factors, including unemployment, lack of quality education, inequality, and governmental failure, which manifest in widespread social ills such as crime, violence, and political instability. Agbaraeke and Alikor (2025) directly linked the causes of youth restiveness to bad governance, corruption, unemployment, and, crucially, a lack of quality functional education. The failure to integrate peer pressure and personality traits into the analysis of youth restiveness has left a critical gap in understanding why some youths become deeply involved in restive behaviors while others in similar conditions do not. These studies have examined youth restiveness from socioeconomic and political standpoints; limited attention has been given to the psychosocial dynamics of peer relationships and personality dispositions in shaping youth behaviors. This study, therefore, aims to bridge these gaps by providing empirical evidence on how these psychological factors contribute to youth restiveness in Kaduna by investigating the role of peer pressure and personality traits on youth restiveness in Kaduna. By gaining a deeper understanding of these factors, the research will contribute to the development of more effective, psychologically informed intervention strategies that cater to the specific needs of at-risk youths, ultimately fostering a more stable and productive society.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of peer pressure on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University?
2. What is the influence of personality traits on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University?
3. What is the joint influence of peer pressure and personality traits on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University?

Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to explore the role of peer pressure and personality traits on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University. Specific objectives include:

1. To examine the influence of peer pressure on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.
2. To evaluate the influence of personality traits on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.
3. To determine the combined influence of peer pressure and personality traits on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested:

1. Peer pressure will significantly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.
2. Personality traits will significantly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.
3. Peer pressure and personality traits will jointly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.

Methods

Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The design involved the collection of data from a population or a representative sample at a single point in time. It provides a structured framework that guides the research process and ensures systematic data collection. Data for the study were obtained through a structured questionnaire administered to participants to assess the influence of peer pressure and personality traits on youth restiveness among students of Kaduna State University. The use of a structured instrument enhances consistency, reduces response bias, and improves the reliability and validity of the data collected. The cross-sectional survey design was considered appropriate for this study because it allows for the efficient collection of data from a large sample within a limited time frame.

Setting

The research was conducted at Kaduna State University main campus, located in Kabala in the Ungwan Rimi/Kaduna North area of Kaduna city, along Tafawa Balewa Way, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Geographically, the main campus sits in an urban setting, surrounded by residential and commercial neighborhoods. Kaduna State is one of the most populous states in northern Nigeria and has experienced various instances of youth restiveness, including violent protests and destruction of public property. The state is divided into 23 Local Government Areas (LGAs), with three zones: Kaduna North, Kaduna Central, and Kaduna South. KASU has 18 faculties and 85 departments. The choice of Kaduna as the research setting is informed by the increasing incidences of youth restiveness in the state, often attributed to socioeconomic challenges, peer group influences, and personality-related factors.

Participants

The participants for this study included youth aged 16–35 years from Kaduna State University (KASU). This age range was chosen because it represents a critical developmental stage where peer influence and personality traits significantly shape behavior. Participants were drawn from different faculties and departments to ensure diverse perspectives on youth restiveness; KASU has 18 faculties and 85 departments. Inclusion criteria required participants to be undergraduate students of KASU within the

specified age range. Exclusion criteria included students outside the age range, postgraduate students, and individuals unwilling to participate. This selection ensured that the study comprehensively explored how peer pressure and personality traits influence youth restiveness among university students in Kaduna.

A total of 370 participants were included in the study. The distribution of respondents by age shows that nearly half of the participants were between 21 and 25 years, accounting for 182 respondents (49.2%). This was followed by those aged 16–20 years with 135 respondents (36.5%). Respondents within the age range of 26–30 years constituted 43 (11.6%), while the least represented group was those aged 32–35 years with 10 respondents (2.7%). This indicates that the majority of respondents were young adults within the typical undergraduate age range.

Regarding gender distribution, the results reveal that 202 respondents (54.6%) were female, while 168 respondents (45.4%) were male.

In terms of religion, the majority of respondents identified as Christians, representing 203 individuals (54.9%). Muslims accounted for 157 respondents (42.4%), while 10 respondents (2.7%) reported practicing other religions. The ethnic distribution of respondents shows that 165 participants (44.6%) were Hausa, representing the largest ethnic group in the sample. Respondents from other ethnic groups accounted for 107 (28.9%). Yoruba respondents constituted 59 (15.9%), while Igbo respondents represented the smallest proportion with 39 individuals (10.5%).

Finally, the distribution of respondents according to level of study indicates that 130 respondents (35.1%) were in 400 level. This was followed by students in 100 level with 103 respondents (27.8%) and 200 level students with 91 respondents (24.6%). Students in 300 level accounted for 46 respondents (12.4%).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A total sample of 370 respondents was selected for the study, determined using Cochran's (1977) finite population formula, as popularized and applied in survey research by Dillman (2000), ensuring adequate representation thus:

$$n = \frac{(N)(p)(1 - p)}{((N - 1)(B / C)^2 + (p)(1 - p))}$$

Where:

$$N = 10,000$$

$$p = 0.5$$

$$B = 0.05$$

$$C = 1.96$$

Therefore:

$$n = 369.8$$

$$n = 370$$

As for the sampling technique, the study employed multistage sampling. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select participants to ensure representation across different faculties and departments within Kaduna State University. In the second stage, proportionate sampling technique was used to select the total number of students in the department. Lastly, systematic sampling technique was used to select the participants by using a sampling interval skip pattern.

Instruments

Three instruments were employed in the study for data collection, consisting of four sections: Section A: demographic information; Section B: The Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS); Section C: the Ten Item Personality Inventory (TIPI); and Section D: the Restiveness Factor Description (RFD). These instruments are further described thus:

Section A: Demographic Information: This section captured the demographic characteristics of participants, including gender, age, religion, ethnicity, and level of study.

Section B: Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS): The Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS), developed by Palani and Mani (2016), was used to assess peer influence on youth behavior. The scale consists of 30 items measuring three dimensions: yielding to peer pressure, resistance to peer pressure, and peer encouragement. Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), with higher scores indicating a stronger influence of peer pressure. Sample items include “I am afraid that I will be left alone if I am not a part of whatever my friends do” and “I am honest with my parents about my whereabouts despite my friends’ objections.” In a study by Oluwole and Afolabi (2022), the scale demonstrated good internal consistency with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.72.

Section C: Ten Item Personality Inventory (TIPI): The Ten Item Personality Inventory, developed by Gosling et al. (2003), was used to measure personality traits. The TIPI is a 10-item measure of the Big Five personality model (2 items each for Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism) rated on a 7-point Likert-type scale ranging from “Strongly disagree” (scored 1) to “Strongly agree” (rated 7). A respondent’s total score in each personality trait was obtained by summing his or her total score on the two items. Higher scores indicate higher ranking in the traits. According to Gosling et al. (2003), the TIPI showed good internal consistency reliability ($\alpha = .83$). Examples of items in the scale include: I see myself as “Extraverted, enthusiastic,” “Critical, quarrelsome,” “Dependable, self-disciplined,” “Anxious, easily upset,” and “Open to new experiences, complex.” The TIPI has been validated in the Nigerian population by Umeaku et al. (2021), who reported good composite internal consistency alpha ($\alpha = .76$).

Section D: Restive Factor Description (RFD): The Restive Description (RFD), developed by Emem et al. (2024), was used to measure the extent of restiveness among youth, particularly in the university setting. It is a 10-item questionnaire consisting of factors that characterize restiveness, rated on a 4-point Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). Sample items include “I protest when my needs are not

met” and “I cannot be still when provoked by students/lecturers.” The RFD has been validated in Nigeria by Emem et al. (2024), and the scale demonstrated good internal consistency with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.78.

Procedure

An introductory letter was taken to the Registrar of Kaduna State University to formally request permission to conduct the study in the institution. Upon receiving approval, the researcher proceeded to the field and collaborated with a few students to assist in locating the different departments and faculties. At initial contact, participants were clearly briefed on the purpose and objectives of the study and assured of confidentiality and voluntary participation. Participants were informed about the importance of providing honest answers without external influence. Participants who expressed willingness to take part in the study were administered the questionnaire, which included informed consent. Only individuals who indicated consent by signing the form proceeded with the questionnaire.

Method of Data Analyses

The data for this study were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27, ensuring accuracy and efficiency in statistical computations. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages, were used to analyze the demographic data of participants. To test the study’s hypotheses, inferential statistics were applied. Standard linear regression was used to analyze the first and second hypotheses, while multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis three.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical guidelines to ensure the welfare, rights, and dignity of participants. The following ethical measures were implemented:

1. **Informed Consent:** All participants were fully informed about the purpose, scope, procedures, and potential risks of the study. Written consent was obtained from each participant, and they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences or need for explanation.
2. **Confidentiality and Anonymity:** To protect participants’ privacy, all data collected were anonymized, and identifying information was excluded from reports and publications. Only the researcher and authorized personnel had access to the data, which were securely stored.
3. **Cultural Sensitivity:** The study was conducted with respect for the cultural and institutional norms of KASU students. All interactions and questions were framed in a culturally appropriate and non-judgmental manner.
4. **Ethical Approval:** Approval for the study was obtained from the relevant institutional review board or ethics committee to ensure adherence to established ethical standards.

5. **Voluntary Participation:** Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any time, without the need for explanation and without facing any consequences.
6. **Transparency:** Participants were informed about the study’s objectives, expected outcomes, and the use of the findings. Clear communication was ensured, and any questions or concerns raised by participants were addressed promptly.

Results

Table 1: Inter-correlation of studied variables

Sn	Variables	Mean	Std	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Age	-	-	1							
2	Gender			-.100	1						
3	Religion			-.136**	-.006	1					
4	Ethnicity			.138**	-.008	-.389**	1				
5	Level			.529**	.111*	-.028	.034	1			
6	Peer Pressure	88.65	14.55	-.112*	.023	.029	.009	-.074	1		
7	Personality	42.32	9.19	.035	.086	-.052	-.017	.007	.339**	1	
8	Restiveness	25.28	6.01	-.088	-.054	.106*	-.122*	.006	.179**	.226**	1

Table 1 presents the inter-correlation matrix among the socio-demographic variables (age, gender, religion, ethnicity, and level of study) and the major study variables (peer pressure, personality, and restiveness). The table also reports the mean and standard deviation for the continuous variables included in the study. With respect to the descriptive statistics, peer pressure recorded a mean score of 88.65 with a standard deviation of 14.55, indicating moderate variability in respondents’ perceived peer influence. Personality had a mean score of 42.32 and a standard deviation of 9.19, suggesting a moderate spread in personality-related responses among participants. Restiveness had a mean score of 25.28 with a standard deviation of 6.01, reflecting some variability in the level of restiveness reported by respondents.

The correlation results show several statistically significant relationships among the socio-demographic variables. Age was positively and significantly related to ethnicity ($r = .138, p < .01$) and level of study ($r = .529, p < .01$). The strong positive relationship between age and level of study suggests that older respondents were more likely to be in higher academic levels. However, age was negatively correlated with religion ($r = -.136, p < .01$) and peer pressure ($r = -.112, p < .05$), indicating that younger respondents tended to report slightly higher levels of peer pressure.

Gender was found to have a weak but significant positive relationship with level of study ($r = .111, p < .05$), suggesting slight variations in academic level distribution across gender. However, gender was not significantly related to age, religion, ethnicity, peer pressure, personality, or restiveness, indicating that these variables were relatively independent of gender differences in the present sample.

Religion demonstrated a significant negative correlation with ethnicity ($r = -.389, p < .01$), suggesting that religious affiliation varied across ethnic groups within the sample. In addition, religion was positively and significantly associated with restiveness ($r = .106, p < .05$), indicating that certain religious affiliations might be slightly related to variations in restiveness among respondents.

Ethnicity also showed a significant negative relationship with restiveness ($r = -.122, p < .05$), suggesting that levels of restiveness varied across different ethnic groups. However, ethnicity was not significantly correlated with peer pressure, personality, or level of study.

Peer pressure demonstrated a significant positive relationship with personality ($r = .339, p < .01$) and restiveness ($r = .179, p < .01$). This implies that higher levels of perceived peer pressure were associated with stronger personality traits measured in the study and increased levels of restiveness among respondents.

Furthermore, personality was positively and significantly correlated with restiveness ($r = .226, p < .01$). This indicates that personality characteristics were related to variations in restiveness, with higher personality scores corresponding to higher reported levels of restiveness.

Hypothesis 1: Peer pressure will significantly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.

Table 2: Standard Linear Regression showing influence of peer pressure on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University

Variable	R	R ²	F	p-value	β	T	p-value
Constant						9.836	0.000
Peer pressure	0.179	0.032	12.11	0.001*	0.179	3.480	<0.01.*

*= Statistically significant

Table 2 presents the results of a standard linear regression analysis examining the influence of peer pressure on restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. The analysis was conducted to determine whether peer pressure significantly predicts restiveness among the respondents. The results indicate that peer pressure significantly predicted restiveness among the youths. The regression model produced a correlation coefficient (R) of .179, suggesting a weak but positive relationship between peer pressure

and restiveness. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was .032, indicating that peer pressure accounted for approximately 3.2% of the variance in restiveness among the respondents.

Furthermore, the overall regression model was statistically significant, as indicated by an F-value of 12.11 with a p-value of .001 ($p < .05$). This suggests that the model significantly explains variations in restiveness and that peer pressure contributes meaningfully to predicting restive behavior among the respondents. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .179$) shows that peer pressure has a positive influence on restiveness. This implies that an increase in peer pressure is associated with an increase in the level of restiveness among the youths. The t-value for peer pressure was 3.480, which was statistically significant at $p < .01$. This further confirms that peer pressure is a significant predictor of restiveness.

Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that peer pressure will significantly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University is hereby confirmed.

Hypothesis 2: Personality traits will significantly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.

Table 3: Standard Linear Regression showing influence of personality on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University

Variable	R	R^2	F	p-value	β	t	p-value
Constant						13.208	0.000
Personality	0.226	0.051	19.88	0.000*	0.226	4.460	<0.01.*

*= Statistically significant

Table 3 presents the results of a standard linear regression analysis examining the influence of personality on restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. The analysis was conducted to determine whether personality significantly predicts restiveness among the respondents.

The results indicate that personality significantly predicted restiveness among the youths in the study. The regression model yielded a correlation coefficient (R) of .226, indicating a positive relationship between personality and restiveness. This suggests that variations in personality characteristics are associated with differences in the level of restiveness among the respondents. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was .051, indicating that personality accounted for approximately 5.1% of the variance in restiveness among the participants. Although this proportion is relatively small, it still suggests that personality contributes to explaining restive behavior among youths in the study area.

Furthermore, the overall regression model was statistically significant, as indicated by an F-value of 19.88 with a p-value of .000 ($p < .05$). This result demonstrates that the model significantly predicts restiveness and that personality is an important explanatory

variable in the model. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .226$) shows that personality has a positive influence on restiveness. This implies that increases in personality scores are associated with increases in the level of restiveness among the youths. The t-value for personality was 4.460, which was statistically significant at $p < .01$, further confirming that personality is a significant predictor of restiveness. Thus, the hypothesis which stated that personality traits will significantly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University is confirmed.

Hypothesis 3: Peer pressure and personality traits will jointly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University.

Table 4: Standard multiple Regression showing of joint influence on restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University

Variable	R	R ²	F	p-value	β	t	p-value
Constant						7.751	0.000
Peer pressure	0.251	0.063	12.32	0.000*	0.115	2.140	0.033*
Personality					0.187	3.490	0.001*

*= Statistically significant

Table 4 presents the results of a standard multiple regression analysis examining the joint and independent influence of peer pressure and personality on restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. The analysis was conducted to determine the combined predictive effect of peer pressure and personality on restiveness, as well as the individual contribution of each variable.

The results indicate that the combined model of peer pressure and personality significantly predicted restiveness among the respondents. The regression model produced a multiple correlation coefficient (R) of .251, indicating a positive relationship between the independent variables (peer pressure and personality) and restiveness. The coefficient of determination (R²) was .063, suggesting that the two predictor variables jointly accounted for approximately 6.3% of the variance in restiveness among the respondents.

Furthermore, the overall regression model was statistically significant, as indicated by an F-value of 12.32 with a p-value of .000 ($p < .05$). This implies that the combined effect of peer pressure and personality significantly explains variations in restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. With respect to the independent contributions of the predictor variables, the findings show that peer pressure made a significant contribution to the prediction of restiveness ($\beta = .115$, $t = 2.140$, $p = .033$). This indicates that peer pressure positively influences restiveness, suggesting that higher levels of peer pressure are associated with increased restive behavior among the respondents.

Similarly, personality also made a significant independent contribution to the prediction of restiveness ($\beta = .187$, $t = 3.490$, $p = .001$). The positive beta coefficient indicates that personality traits are positively related to restiveness, meaning that variations in personality characteristics contribute to differences in restive behavior among youths. Overall, the findings demonstrate that both peer pressure and personality jointly and independently influence restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. However, personality appears to be a slightly stronger predictor of restiveness than peer pressure, as indicated by its higher beta coefficient and t-value. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that peer pressure and personality traits will jointly influence restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University is hereby confirmed.

Discussion

The study investigated peer pressure and personality traits as determinants of restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University (KASU). Three hypotheses were tested using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 to analyze the data. The descriptive statistics used were frequency, percentages, means, and standard deviations, while the inferential statistics used for the test of hypotheses 1 and 2 were simple linear regression, and multiple linear regression analysis was used to test hypothesis 3. The findings are therefore discussed thus.

The first hypothesis posited that peer pressure would significantly influence youth restiveness among youth in Kaduna State University and was confirmed. Standard linear regression demonstrated that peer pressure significantly predicted restiveness among the youths. The findings of this study revealed that peer pressure significantly predicts restiveness. This implies that peer pressure on restiveness among youths is shaped by social interaction and group dynamics. The need for acceptance, belonging, and identity formation often makes individuals more likely to adopt the attitudes and behaviors of their peers, even when such behaviors are deviant or socially undesirable. This result is consistent with findings of previous studies, including Onwuchekwe et al. (2025) on youth behavior in Anambra State; their study found that peer group pressure significantly influences youths' involvement in cybercrime, demonstrating how peer networks can encourage engagement in antisocial activities. Similarly, research by Yusuf et al. (2025) on antisocial behavior among students in Nasarawa State revealed that negative peer pressure is a significant predictor of deviant behaviors, reinforcing the idea that peer influence plays a critical role in shaping maladaptive conduct. Ezecheta (2025), in a study on youth restiveness in Nasarawa State, identified peer group influence as one of the key determinants of restive actions such as aggression, protest, and resistance to authority. These studies align with the present study, suggesting that peer pressure contributes to the manifestation of restiveness within university settings.

The second hypothesis posited that personality traits will significantly influence restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University and was confirmed. Standard linear regression demonstrated that personality significantly predicted restiveness among the youths in the study, indicating a positive relationship between personality and restiveness. This result implies that individual differences in behavioral tendencies,

emotional regulation, and psychological dispositions play a crucial role in shaping how youths respond to their environment. Personality traits influence how individuals perceive situations, react to challenges, and manage impulses. This result aligns with a recent study by Agnieszka et al. (2025). Their study on personality traits and aggressive behavior revealed that neuroticism showed a strong positive relationship with general aggressiveness, indicating that individuals who are more emotionally unstable are more likely to experience anger, hostility, and aggressive tendencies. This is particularly relevant to the present study, as such emotional tendencies can easily translate into restive behaviors in a university setting. Additionally, their findings showed that openness to experience was positively associated with physical aggression and hostility, suggesting that individuals who are more open to experiences may also be more inclined to explore or engage in unconventional or risky behaviors, including aggression, which can also translate into restive behaviors. In addition, the findings of this study are in line with the work of Neboh and Eze (2020), who investigated personality traits as determinants of antisocial behavior among university students in South-East Nigeria. Their study revealed that personality traits significantly influence students' involvement in antisocial behaviors such as rule-breaking, destruction of property, risky behaviors, and other forms of misconduct.

The third hypothesis posited that peer pressure and personality traits will jointly influence restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University and was confirmed. The findings of this study supported this hypothesis, indicating that both peer pressure and personality traits jointly and independently predict restive behavior among the respondents. The result implies that youth restiveness is not caused by a single factor but rather by the interaction between environmental influences and individual psychological characteristics. Peer pressure represents an external social force, while personality traits reflect internal predispositions. The combined influence of these variables suggests that restiveness emerges from the interplay between what youths experience in their social environment and how they are psychologically wired to respond. The result of this finding is supported by the social cognitive theory proposed by Bandura (1986), which emphasizes reciprocal determinism, the dynamic interaction between personal factors, environmental influences, and behavior. According to this theory, individuals are not passive recipients of peer influence; rather, their personality traits shape how they interpret and respond to such social pressures. Thus, peer pressure may provide the situational context for restiveness, while personality determines behavioral expression. This aligns with research by Gardner and Steinberg (2005). Their study demonstrated that the presence of peers significantly increases risk-taking behavior, especially among individuals who are already predisposed to impulsivity. The result is also in harmony with the findings of Allen et al. (2006). They found that individuals differ in their susceptibility to peer influence, and this susceptibility is shaped by personal characteristics. This suggests that personality moderates the effect of peer pressure, meaning that not every individual responds to peer influence in the same way.

The findings of this study also align with the research by Miller and Lynam (2001), who conducted a comprehensive meta-analytic review of the relationship between personality and antisocial behavior. Their findings demonstrated that specific personality traits,

particularly high neuroticism, low agreeableness, and low conscientiousness, are consistently and strongly associated with aggressive tendencies, conduct problems, and externalizing behaviors across diverse samples. When such personality characteristics interact with peer environments that encourage aggression or defiance, the likelihood of restive behavior increases significantly. This meta-analytic evidence reinforces the present study's finding that peer pressure and personality traits are meaningful predictors of restiveness among youths.

Conclusion

The findings of this study illustrated that peer pressure and personality traits are significant determinants of restiveness among youths in Kaduna State University. The results showed that peer pressure has a positive and significant influence on restiveness, indicating that the social environment and interactions within peer groups contribute to the development of restive behaviors. Similarly, personality traits were found to significantly influence restiveness, with a stronger effect, suggesting that individual psychological characteristics such as emotional stability, impulsivity, and self-control play a more dominant role in shaping behavior. Furthermore, the joint influence of peer pressure and personality traits highlights that restiveness is not caused by a single factor but emerges from the interaction between environmental and individual factors. However, the researcher concluded that personality traits are the dominant factor, suggesting that strengthening emotional regulation, self-control, and adaptive behavioral patterns serves as the most effective protective mechanism against restiveness among youths, even in the presence of peer pressure.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this research, the following five recommendations are proposed:

- 1. Peer Influence Management Programs:** University authorities should establish structured programs such as peer mentoring and positive peer group initiatives to reduce negative peer pressure and promote healthy social interactions among students.
- 2. Psychological and Counseling Services:** Universities should strengthen counseling units to provide personality-focused interventions aimed at improving emotional regulation, self-control, and adaptive behavioral patterns among students.
- 3. Personality Development Programs:** Educational programs and workshops should be developed to help students understand their personality traits and how these traits influence their behavior, thereby reducing tendencies toward restiveness.
- 4. Student Engagement Activities:** Institutions should create platforms such as leadership programs, student clubs, and extracurricular activities that channel students' energy into productive and socially acceptable behaviors.

5. **Awareness and Sensitization Campaigns:** Regular seminars and awareness campaigns should be organized to educate students on the effects of negative peer pressure and the importance of making independent and responsible decisions.
6. **Early Identification and Intervention:** University management should implement systems to identify students exhibiting signs of restiveness early and provide timely psychological and behavioral support.

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